

The Effects of Aqueous Eucalyptus (*Eucalyptus Globulus* Labill.). Leaf Extract in the Control of Early Development of Leaf Spot Disease (Cercosporiosis) Of Groundnuts (*Arachis Hypogaea* L.)

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Abstract

This study evaluated the effectiveness of the aqueous eucalyptus leaf extract (AELE) in the control of early cercosporiosis of groundnut (*Arachis hypogaea* L.) at Meyos, a suburb of Yaoundé, Cameroon. It was two factors factorial experimental, with two varieties of groundnuts (JL24 and "Bafia") and five treatments (T_0 : control; T_1 , T_2 , T_3 : consisting of 25, 50, 100 g/l of extract respectively) and T_4 (treated with synthetic fungicide). The disease was identified at the field; and the growth, epidemiology and yield parameters of plants were assessed. Field observations of symptoms and microscopic observations of the pure strain confirmed the nature of the disease. The use of different treatments did not influence significantly ($P=0.05$) the growth parameters of both varieties of groundnuts. At a dose of 100 g/l of the extract, the disease incidence significantly reduced compared to the control. At 28 days and 56 days after sowing, plants treated with fungicide had the least disease incidence (68.57 and 60.62 % respectively) in the JL24 variety and 69.47 and 62.52 % respectively in the "Bafia" variety and these were significantly different from control (100 %). The disease severity was least with fungicide treated plants 7.5, and 15.4 % as compared with control (13.1 and 73.4% in the JL24 variety; 8.6, and 16.3 for the "Bafia" variety while its control was 14.7 and 79.3 % respectively). The dry pods yield was highest in plots treated with synthetic fungicide (2.18 and 1.83 t/ha in the JL24 and "Bafia" varieties respectively) than with aqueous extract at a dose of 100 g/l (1.99 and 1.71 t/ha for the respective varieties while plants in their control plots had yield of 1.59 and 1.18t/ha for the respective species).

Key words: Groundnut varieties, leaf spot disease, aqueous eucalyptus leaf extract, growth, yield.

Introduction

Groundnut is a Fabaceae and a tropical herbaceous plant native of South America and it is the sixth most important oilseed crop in the world (Koita *et al.*, 2017). It is a very important cash and subsistence crop in several African countries such as Cameroon (Ntare, 2007). This legume is produced in all regions of Cameroon. In the northern region of Cameroon, it covers about 43 % of cultivated areas, 39 % of national production and 41 % of farmers (Betdogo *et al.*, 2015). It ranks second after cotton from a monetary stand point in the northern part of Cameroon (Kouebou *et al.* 2013). In 2019, the world production was 48,756,790 tons with a yield of 1,647.4 kg / ha while Africa produced 16,636,818 tons with an average of 970.3 kg / ha. In Cameroon its main producers are small-scale farmers, with 608,731 tons in 2015 with a yield of 1,397.6 kg / ha to 594,019 tons in 2019 with a yield of 1,203.6 kg / ha (Anonymous, 2021). It grows best on sandy loam soils with rainfall that exceeds 500mm/annum. The crop has economic potentials and aid in the reduction of poverty and enhances food security in sub-Saharan Africa (Christiaensen *et al* 2011). It is a good source of non-cholesterol oil, good of protein and its cake is used in the production of animal feed. High pest pressure and shifts in the sowing date due to climate change substantially reduced productivity in

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the plantations (Ambang *et al.*, 2001). Several diseases are responsible for huge yield losses. Among them is early Cercosporiosis, with yield losses of more than 50 % (Ntoukam *et al.*, 1996).

To control this disease, chemical control is the most widely used and it is the most effective despite its harmful effects. Improved varieties used in genetic control do not totally resist phytopathogens. In the search for alternatives, many plants are reported in the literature with pesticidal properties against a large number of phytoparasites; they include *Azadirachta indica*, *Thevetia peruviana*, *Jatropha curcas* and *Eucalyptus* (Ndogho *et al.*, 2018; Dida *et al.*, 2019; Tsompbeng *et al.*, 2014). In view of the biopesticide features of *Eucalyptus*, its efficacy in the control of early Cercosporiosis caused by *Cercospora arachidicola* could be an alternative in plant protection domain.

Materials and Methods

Description of the study site

The experiment was carried out in “Meyos” in the centre Region of Cameroon. The study site is located in agroecological zone V of Cameroon and it lies between latitude 4°10” and 4°20” N and longitude 11°30” and 11° 35” E. It has a bimodal rainfall zone with mean annual rainfall range of 1500 to 1800mm while temperatures varying between 23 - 35°C and relative humidity of 83%. The soils are red ferrallitic and acidic soils and the vegetation is humid forest.

Plant materials and fungicide

The plant material consisted of two varieties of groundnut (“Bafia” was bought from the Yaoundé central market and JL24 was obtained from the Institute of Agricultural Research for Development (IRAD) Garoua and ground eucalyptus leaves were collected in Yaoundé and oven dried at 50° C for 72 hours and later ground to powder. MONCHAMP 720 WP is the synthetic fungicide used and this is made up of 120 g/kg of cymoxanil + 600 g/kg of mancozeb and applied at the recommended dose of 3.33 g/l. The aqueous eucalyptus leaf extract was prepared according 25 g/L; 50 g/L and 100 g/L of water as described by -----

Experimental design

The experimental design used was a two factors factorial with two factors. The main factor consisted of the groundnut varieties and the subplots were 5 treatments which are: T₀ (control), T₁, T₂, T₃ (25, 50 and 100 g/l of extract respectively); T₄ (3.33 g/l of synthetic fungicide); and the second factor varieties JL24 and “Bafia”. The land was cleared, ploughed, flatly ridged to a height of 25 cm. The plot size was 3 x 4 m² with a gap of 2 m between plots and 3 m between replicates there were three replications The planting dimension was 40 x 30 cm and two seeds were planted per hole to a depth of 5-7 cm. One weeks after germination the seedlings were thinned to one plant/stand and the population density per hectare was 83,333plants/ha Weeds were managed by hand weeding when necessary. A week after germination, the plants were spray according to the various treatments. Some growth parameters were assessed from 28 days after sowing and measurements were done weakly until the 56th day after sowing when the plants were flowering.

Effect of extract on growth parameters

Three parameters were evaluated namely the plant height, the number of leaves and branches. The height of the plant was measured with a meter rule from the soil surface to the apex of the plant. The number of leaves and branches was obtained by counting on plants from the fourth week after sowing (WAS) and every week until flowering.

Effect of treatments on the disease

Plants having disease symptoms were identified, tagged with strings and counted. The two main parameters of the disease were assessed, incidence and severity. These were calculated by adopting the following formulas:

For the incidence (I), it is $I (\%) = \frac{Nd_p}{Nt} \times 100$;equation 1

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where I = disease incidence on an area; N_{dp} = number of diseased plants on an area; N_t = total number of plants in the area.

The severity (S) was estimated from the degree of leaf infection by the disease using a disease identification scale. The formula is: $S (\%) = \frac{\sum ab}{N} \times 100$, equation 2

where S = severity of infection; $\sum (ab)$ = the sum of the multiplications of the number of disease plants (a) by the degree of infection (b) given in (%); N = total number of diseased plants.

The scale for the degree of infection (b) as described by Wangungu *et al.* (2011) where 0 = 0 % plant infection; 1 = infection covering between 1 and 15 % of the plant; 2 = infection covering between 16 and 40 % of the plant; 3 = infection covering between 41 and 75 %; 4 = infection covering between 76 and 100 % of the plant.

The effect of treatments on the yield of two varieties of groundnuts.

The harvest was carried out manually in each plot after yellowing and senescence of the older leaves. The number of pods per plant was determined per treatment and the variety. The weight of fresh pods and later that of dry pods were measured using a sensitive scale. After dehulling these pods, one hundred (100) seeds from each treatment were weighed to assess their dry weight. The calculated yield was estimated in tons per hectare following the formula used by Svecnjak *et al.* (2006):

$$R (t/ha) = \frac{AWP \times NP}{A} \times 10000, \dots\dots\dots \text{equation 3}$$

where AWP= average yield /per plant; NP=Number of plants per elementary plot; A=Area of each elementary plot; 10000 m² = 1 ha.

Data analysis

The data collected in the field was processed in the Excel 2016 spread sheet possible to draw the graphs and tables related to this study. The data was subjected to multivariate analysis of variance (MANOVA) using SPSS software (Version 20.0). DMRT (Duncan`s Multi-Range Test) at 5 % was used to compare means for significant differences.

Results

Symptoms observes in the field

Three weeks after sowing, the phenotypic observation of groundnut plants showed small black or dark brown spots on upper surface of leaves. On some leaves, the yellowing of the infected part accompanied these spots. These are the characteristic symptoms of Cercosporiosis of groundnut (Fig.1).

Fig.1. Groundnut leaves of showing symptoms of a leaf spot

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Effect of treatments on the growth parameters**Plant height**

The plant heights varied very little between the different treatments. At 63 days after sowing, the highest plant height was observed in control (34.2 cm) and the least height was in plant treated with fungicide in variety JL24. For the variety "Bafia" the highest height was with plant treated with 50% eucalyptus leaf extract. There was no significant difference ($P=0.05$) in height for both groundnut varieties (Fig.2).

Fig.2. Variation of plant height in different treatments (A. JL24 variety; B. Bafia variety; T₀: control; T₁; T₂; T₃: treated with 25; 50 and 100 g/l of extract; T₄: treated with chemical fungicide). Values followed by the same letter on the histograms are not significantly different according to Duncan test at 5 %

2.2 Effect of treatments on the number of leaves of two groundnut varieties

The number of leaves was not significantly different ($P=0.05$) with treatments throughout the observation period for both varieties of groundnuts (Fig.3). 63 days after sowing, the number of leaves was highest in plant treated with 25 and 50% eucalyptus leaf extract (38) and the least was in the other treatment (37) for

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variety JL24 (Fig.3a). The highest leaves number was recorded in plant treated with fungicide (37) and least was in other treatment (36) for “Bafia” variety (Fig.3b).

Fig.3. Variation of the number of leaves in different treatments with time (A - JL24 variety; B Bafia variety; T₀: control; T₁; T₂; T₃: treated with 25; 50 and 100 g/l of extract; T₄: treated with chemical fungicide). Values with the same letter on the histograms are not significantly different at P=0.05.

Number of branches

There was no significant difference in the number of branches with respect to the treatments in both varieties of groundnut (Table I). All of the plant a mean number of branches (11).

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Table I. The effects of various treatments on the number of branches.

Varieties	Treatments	Number of branches					
		28 days	35 days	42 days	49 days	56 days	63 days
JL24	T0	4,3 ± 0,16a	5,2 ± 0,75a	7,0 ± 1,01a	9,7 ± 0,86a	11,0 ± 0,78 a	11,0 ± 0,78 a
	T1	4,3 ± 1,02a	5,3 ± 1,07a	7,4 ± 0,80a	9,7 ± 1,09a	10,9 ± 0,69 a	10,9 ± 0,69 a
	T2	4,2 ± 0,56a	5,7 ± 0,96a	7,2 ± 1,16a	9,7 ± 1,26a	11,0 ± 1,02 a	11,0 ± 1,02 a
	T3	4,2 ± 0,78a	5,9 ± 0,87a	7,5 ± 1,03a	9,0 ± 0,97a	11,3 ± 1, 23 a	11,3 ± 1, 23 a
	T4	4,6 ± 0,91a	5,4 ± 1,03a	7,3 ± 0,57a	9,9 ± 0,73a	11,2 ± 1,09 a	11,2 ± 1,09 a
Bafia	T0	4,3 ± 1,01a	6,3 ± 0,77a	7,6 ± 0,95a	9,8 ± 1,13a	11,0 ± 1,33 a	11,0 ± 1,33 a
	T1	4,1 ± 0,86a	6,2 ± 1,25a	7,3 ± 1,26a	9,8 ± 1,31a	11,0 ± 1,17 a	11,0 ± 1,17 a
	T2	4,6 ± 1,30a	6,5 ± 1,02a	7,6 ± 0,89a	9,8 ± 0,92a	11,0 ± 0,91 a	11,0 ± 0,91 a
	T3	4,8 ± 0,80a	6,4 ± 1,16a	7,7 ± 1,17a	9,0 ± 0,58a	10,9 ± 1,04 a	10,9 ± 1,04 a
	T4	4,1 ± 1,24a	6,5 ± 0,98a	7,7 ± 1,09a	9,7 ± 1,00a	11,2 ± 0,99 a	11,2 ± 0,99 a

T₀: control; T₁; T₂; T₃: treated with 25; 50 and 100 g/l of extract; T₄: treated with chemical fungicide. The values with the same letter in the column for each variety are not significantly different at DMT 5 %.

Effect of treatments on the development of the disease

The disease incidence

The disease incidence showed significant differences with treatments (P=0.05). The least disease incidence was recorded in plant treated with fungicide both at 28 and 56 days after sowing for both varieties (22.38 and 60.62 %) for JL24 variety and (23.68 and 62.52 %) for “Bafia” variety (Fig.4). The highest incidence at 28 and 56 days was in plant in control and those plants treated with 25 % aqueous eucalyptus leaf extract for variety JL 24 (42.93 and 100 % in the control; 42.42 and 100 % in those with 25 % of leaf extract while for “Bafia” variety the disease incidence at 28 and 56 DAS was highest in control (42,92 and 100 %) and plant treated with 25 g/L of AELE (44,38 and 100 % respectively).

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Fig.4. Incidence of early Cercosporiosis in different treatments (A - JL24 variety; B - “Bafia” variety; T₀: control; T₁; T₂; T₃: treated with 25; 50 and 100 g/l of extract; T₄: treated with chemical fungicide). Values with the same letter on the histograms are not significantly different at (0.05)

Effect of treatments on the severity of Cercosporiosis of two varieties of groundnut

The disease showed significant differences with treatments (P=0.05). The least disease severity was recorded on plant treated with fungicide both at 28 and 56 days after sowing for both varieties (7.5 and 15.4 %) for JL24 variety; (8.5 and 16.3 %) for “Bafia” variety (Fig.5). The highest severity at 28 and 56 days was in plant in control and those treated with 25 % aqueous eucalyptus leaf extract for variety JL 24 (13.1 and 73.4 % in the control; 12.7 and 72.7 % on those with 25 % of leaf extract) ; for “Bafia” variety (14.7 and 79.0 % in the control; 13.9 and 77.4 % in those plants with 25 % of leaf extract).

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Fig. 5. Evolution of the severity of early Cercosporiosis in different treatments: (A - JL24 variety and B - “Bafia” variety); T₀: control; T₁; T₂; T₃: treated with 25; 50 and 100 g/l of extract; T₄: treated with chemical fungicide) The values with the same letter on the histograms are not significantly different according at P =0.05

The effect of various treatments on the fresh pod yield of two varieties of groundnuts.

Number of pods per plant

There was a significant difference with the number of pods per plants for the various treatments in both varieties. The highest number of pods per plant in JL 24 was 23 and the least was in the control (18) (Table 2). For “Bafia” variety, the highest number was with plants treated with fungicide (14) and the least in the control (11) (Table 3).

Average number of seeds per pod

There was no significant difference with the number of seed per pods in various treatments in both varieties. The mean number for JL24 was 2 (Table 2) and for “Bafia” was \approx 3 (Table 3).

Yield of fresh pods

There was a significant difference with the yield of fresh pods for the various treatments in both varieties. For JL 24, the highest fresh pod yield was 4.02 t/ha in plot treated with fungicide and the least (3.26 t/ha) in the control (Table 2). For “Bafia” variety, the highest yield was 3.47 t/ha and the least was 2.28 t/ha (Table 3).

Effect of treatments on dry pod yield

There is a significant difference (P=0.05) with the yield of dry pods for the various treatments in both varieties. For JL24, the highest yield was 2.18 t/ha and the least was 1.59 t/ha in plots treated with 25 g/L of AELE (Table 2). For “Bafia” variety, the highest dry pod yield was 1.83 t/ha in plot treated with fungicide and the least was 1.18 t/ha in the control plots (Table 3).

Dry weight of 100 seeds

There were significance differences with respect to dry weight of 100 seeds for the various treatments in both varieties. For JL24, the highest 100 seed weight was in plants treated with fungicide (52.6 g) and the least was 48.3 g in the control (Table 2). For “Bafia” variety, the highest 100 seeds weight was in plants treated with fungicide (36.9 g) and the least was 33.5 g in the control plots (Table 3).

Table 2. The effect of different treatments on the yield parameters for JL24 groundnut Variety.

Treatments	Yield parameters				
	Average number of seeds / pods	Average number of pods / plants	Yield of fresh pods (t/ha)	Yield of dry pods (t/ha)	Dry weight of 100 seeds (g)
T ₀	2,0 a	18,51 ± 1,02 a	3,26 a	1.59 a	48.3 a
T ₁	2,0 a	18,67 ± 0,75 a	3,33 a	1.57 a	48.5 a
T ₂	2,0 a	19,32 ± 2,01 a	3,58 ab	1.72 a	48.9 a
T ₃	2,0 a	21,43 ± 1,74 b	3,89 b	1.99 b	50.8 b
T ₄	2,0 a	23,17 ± 0,83 b	4,02 c	2.18 b	52.6 c

T₀: control treatment; T₁: treatment with aqueous extract of eucalyptus leaves at 25 g/l; T₂: treatment with aqueous extract of eucalyptus leaves at 50 g/l; T₃: treatment with aqueous extract of eucalyptus leaves at 100 g/l; T₄: synthetic fungicide treatment. The values with the same letter on the histograms are not significantly different according to P=0.5.

Table 3. The effect of different treatments on the yield parameters for “Bafia” groundnut Variety.

Treatments	Yield parameters				
	Average number of seeds / pods	Average number of pods / plants	Yield of fresh pods (t/ha)	Yield of Dry pods (t/ha)	Dry weight of 100 seeds (g)
T ₀	3,67 a	11,23 ± 1,07a	2,28 a	1.18 a	33.5 a
T ₁	3,61 a	11,79 ± 0,89a	2,52 a	1.25 a	33.8 a
T ₂	3,69 a	12,45 ± 1,18 a	2,97 b	1.36 a	34.2 a
T ₃	3,65 a	13,83 ± 0,62 b	3,14 b	1.71 b	35.7 b
T ₄	3,71 a	14,36 ± 1,09 b	3,47 c	1.83 b	36.9 c

T₀: control treatment; T₁: treatment with aqueous extract of eucalyptus leaves at 25 g/l; T₂: treatment with aqueous extract of eucalyptus leaves at 50 g/l; T₃: treatment with aqueous extract of eucalyptus leaves at 100 g/l; T₄: synthetic fungicide treatment. The values with the same letter in the columns are not significantly different at P= 0.5

Discussion

The symptoms observed in the field were similar to those of leaf spot disease of groundnuts. Microscopic observations of the pure isolate obtained, helped to highlight rounded spores of dark brown and orange yellow colouring, and long transverse filaments. Morphological features of spores were similar to those reported by Chauvegeon (1956) on cercosporiosis of peanut, (*Cercospora arachidicola*) which is responsible for early cercosporiosis of groundnut.

Assessment of plant growth parameters including plant height, number of leaves and branches showed no significant difference between the treatments with time for the two varieties. This could be due to their genetic factors. Mboudou (2020) obtained similar results using the aqueous extract of *Thevetia peruviana* in the control of corn stalk borer in the field. The evaluation of the epidemiological parameters (incidence and severity) on the cercosporiosis in the field showed its gradual spread in plots depending on the treatments and varieties. Unlike the smallest dose of the extract used (25 g/l), the other two doses showed an influence on the incidence of the disease with a significant effect to control disease obtained with the dose of 100 g/l. This suggests that in a low dose of the aqueous eucalyptus leaf extract (AELE) the concentration of secondary metabolites was low in restricting the spread of the disease in the field. Tobdem (2004) obtained similar results when using AELE in the control of some diseases of millet and sorghum; the effectiveness of the extract was observed from the dose of 40 g/l unlike the control. At a dose of 100 g/l, the efficacy of AELE was statistically different from that of the synthetic fungicide. Thus, the use of AELE in relatively higher doses might give similar results as that of the chemical fungicide. Ndogho *et al.* (2018) noted similar results with the aqueous extract of neem seeds at a dose of 100 g/l that had the same efficacy as those of chemical fungicide in the control of Asian rust of soybean.

Different treatments applied to the plants greatly reduced the severity of early cercosporiosis in the field. Nevertheless, plants in the control plots and those treated with 25 g/l of eucalyptus leaf extract (T₁) recorded the highest severity. These values were low in treatments T₃ and T₄ in the two varieties respectively. This may be as a result of high concentration of secondary metabolites such as alkaloids, anthraquinones, flavonoids and saponins in eucalyptus leaves (Tamsa, 2017). The average number of seeds per pod recorded in the different treatments was 2.0 for the JL24 variety and ≈ 3 for the Bafia variety. This would be due to the genetic characteristics of each variety.

The highest number of pods per plant was obtained in plots treated with 100g/L plant extract and fungicide. This difference in the number of pods per plant could be due to the genetic potentials of each variety. Betdogo *et al.* (2015) during their work with five groundnut cultivars in the northern region of Cameroon, recorded average values 37 and 28 pods per plant respectively in the ICG 3312 and ICG 1471 varieties respectively. The highest pod yield for JL24 variety was in plots treated with 100g/L plant extract and fungicide and this might be due higher photosynthetic rate on the leave surfaces as result of low severity of the disease when compared with other treatments. These yields are close to those obtained by Asafor *et al.* (2020) who used neem (*Azadirachta indica*) and garlic (*Allium sativum*) extracts in the control of groundnut leaf spot diseases (*Arachis hypogaea* L.) and obtained an average yield of fresh pods 4.60 ± 1.17 t/ha, 4.93 ± 1.05 t/ha and 4.16 ± 1.14 t/ha respectively in the “Fleur 11”; “65-13” and local (“Village”) varieties. The highest 100 seeds weight for JL24 variety was in plots treated 100g/L leaf extract (50.8 g) and fungicide (52.6 g). These results are similar to those of Ndekani (2014) in a comparative study of the yields of four groundnut varieties in the soil of Mbanza-Ngungu obtained a dry weight of 52.85 g for 100 seeds of the JL24 variety

Conclusion

The aqueous eucalyptus leaf extract of 100g/L applied in the field was effective in controlling early cercosporiosis and increasing groundnut yield. It could be used as an alternative to synthetic fungicides in the context of integrated pest management against pathogens that attack groundnuts in the field. Thus, this method of control is part of the agroecological transition which today remains a major concern. It was also noted that the JL24 variety is less susceptible to early cercosporiosis and produces good yields compared to Bafia, thus it could be advisable for farmers to cultivate more of this improve groundnut variety.

Conflict of interest: The authors acknowledge that there is no conflict of interest.

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